

BEYOND TASTE: EFFECTIVENESS OF TEAM-BASED AND VIDEO-BASED APPROACHES ON STUDENTS' PLATE PRESENTATION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The shift in education caused the teachers to use different methodologies and learning strategies to cater to the needs of the students. Given the hands-on nature of cooking instruction, it is crucial for instructors to use teaching approaches that optimize students' learning experiences to enhance their plate presentation skills. This study looked into the effectiveness of the Team-based and Video-based learning approaches on the plate presentation skills of cookery students. A quasi-experimental design was employed. Statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and t-test for paired samples were used to assess the level of plate presentation skills before and after the implementation of interventions. Additionally, ANCOVA was utilized to compare the effectiveness of the two approaches. One group was exposed to team-based learning while another group was exposed to the video-based learning. The findings revealed a significant increase in the post-test plate presentation skills score for both groups. Specifically, students in the team-based learning group received very good ratings on proper balance, color, shape and garnish. In contrast, students in video-based learning group received very good ratings in color, shape, and garnish, but only a good rating in proper balance. The data indicate that both approaches significantly influence students' plating skills across all sub-skills. However, the video-based learning was found to be more effective than the team-based learning in improving shape and use of garnish. However, it is the team-based that is more effective in improving balance. The study points to the need for teachers to consider utilizing collaborative activities for students to work and learn from their peers and even share their knowledge. Moreover, it suggests the use of video discussions or tutorial videos as effective tools for teaching new skills.

Key Words: *Plate presentation skills, Team-based learning, Video-based learning*

INTRODUCTION

The Cookery NCII Qualification is a comprehensive program aimed at equipping individuals with the necessary competencies to effectively achieve specific tasks (TESDA, 2014). Derived from the competency map of the Tourism Sector's Hotel and Restaurant domain, a key component of this qualification involves the preparation of meat dishes (Unit Code: TRS512338). To excel in this aspect, candidates must demonstrate the ability to present meat dishes attractively while adhering to classical, cultural, and enterprise standards wherein plate presentation is a skill that they need to master.

Plate presentation is the final phase in culinary presentation and is critical for displaying the quality of food while engaging guests' senses (The Culinary Pro, 2023). Moreover, food presentation and plating are important parts of culinary arts that play an important role in attracting guests and creating the environment of a restaurant (The Art of Food Preparation, 2022). With these, professional chefs' plate presentation talents include a variety of techniques such as color coordination, garnishing, and stacking, which highlight the creativity and artistic aptitude of culinary specialists and contribute to both visual appeal and flavor (Smith and Jones, 2018).

Given the hands-on nature of cooking instruction, instructors should use teaching approaches that optimize students' learning experiences. Traditional tactics such as straight talk or PowerPoint presentations may not be beneficial in improving plate presentation skills. As a result, an experimental approach integrating team-based learning and video-based learning is required to establish their impact on TVL students' plate presentation skills (Kazi et al., 2021).

Finally, the purpose is to provide students with effective learning methodologies and to promote their growth in this crucial culinary area, ensuring that the future generation of chefs can master the art of plate presentation and create outstanding dining experiences for their clients.

Framework

This study assumed that that team-based and video-based learning approaches are facilitative of the development of TVL students' plate presentation skills. This study is anchored on the theory of Constructivism of Jean Piaget and the Multimedia Learning Theory of Richard Mayer. Constructivist learning theory which is anchored from McLeod's (2023) conceptualization, is a teaching methodology shaped by the integration of dynamic, experiential, and hands-on aspects of culinary education, establishing a theoretical foundation to incorporate and master the plate presentation skills.

A recent study by Rodriguez et al. (2019) shows that culinary education can be more empowered and enhanced with the assistance of active participation by the students. In line with the constructivist learning theory, knowledge is actively constructed by students through interactions, practical experiences, and reflective processes.

Moreover, Chen et al.'s recent research (2020) emphasizes the value of social contacts in the development of culinary skills. The cooperative efforts that are highlighted in team-based learning are consistent with research indicating that knowledge in the culinary domain is constructed through interactions and shared experiences with peers, teachers, and the culinary environment.

Team-based learning (TBL), as defined by Parmalee and Michaelsen (2010), is an instructional strategy that promotes collaborative learning and teamwork among students to enhance understanding of the course and develop the skills necessary to complete the course. It has different kind of strategies such as team formation, application activities, peer teaching, team reflection, and inter-team competition. First, team formation is a TBL strategy that has a big impact to the learning process of the students because of how successful and effective it can be, wherein students will be given the opportunity to work in team wherein they can share ideas, their skills in cooking, and guide their teammates (Parmalee & Michaelsen, 2010). Peer-teaching allows the students to closely work within a member to improve learning and skill, a peer take turns in leading the task in preparing meals and assist each other to discuss ideas and outline strategies and divide tasks to finish the task easily (Haidet, et.al., 2014). Fourth, team reflection encourages students in ongoing team progress wherein they can evaluate their performance and pinpoint their strengths for potential growth of the team and weaknesses to improve for the next team activity.

The Multimedia Learning Theory (MLT), developed by Richard Mayer, provides a valuable framework for educators to enhance the educational experience by harnessing technology's potential in the classroom (Ramlatachan, 2019).

Moreover, MLT centers on the idea that when educators utilize various tools and mediums, such as audio and visuals, they can more effectively engage students and cater to the diverse ways in which individuals learn. According to Mayer, as cited by Ramlatchan (2019), combining different types of information—like words and pictures—makes learning easier and more effective since it aligns with how the brain works during learning.

The Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Home Economics Cookery strand under the senior high school curriculum requires the students to acquire a set of competencies and skills essential to the cooking industry (DepEd and TESDA). With constructivist learning theory and multimedia learning theory, educators will be able to provide the students with the opportunity to improve their skills. Since cooking is a life skill that requires a lot of skills, it is important for the students to learn how to work with others, learn from each other, and use available resources to improve themselves.

At the core of this study is the exploration of plate presentation skills among TVL students. Plate presentation skills among cookery students have evolved significantly in recent years, reflecting broader shifts in culinary education and industry demands. A holistic approach to plate presentation is emphasized in contemporary literature,

incorporating aspects of aesthetics, cultural sensitivity, sustainability, and technical innovation. Cookery students are now encouraged to not only master the technical aspects of cooking but also develop a keen eye for balance, harmony, and creativity in their presentations. Research by Garcia and Rodriguez (2022) emphasizes the value of cultural sensitivity in accommodating a range of tastes and preferences.

Moreover, Chen et al. (2020) examine how technological developments are being incorporated into plate presentation techniques, offering students new avenues for creativity and innovation.

Furthermore, contemporary culinary arts literature acknowledges the potency of vibrant hues as a dynamic tool in the chef's palette. Chen et al. (2022) emphasizes the use of vibrant colors as a powerful component of the multisensory experience offered to diners. The integration of vibrant hues is seen as a deliberate strategy in creating a sensory symphony that goes beyond taste, engaging sight and enhancing the overall enjoyment of a dish. This study aligns with the evolving nature of culinary arts, where chefs are increasingly viewed as orchestrators of holistic dining experiences.

The figure 1 shows the use of two interventions, team—based learning and video-based learning, in determining the plate presentation skills of the students. The plate presentation skills with 5 criteria: proper balance, use of color, shape (proportion), use of garnish, and overall presentation; will be evaluated before and after the implementation of the intervention. A pre-test will be implemented to measure the plate presentation skill of the students and a post-test to measure the skill of the students after a month-long implementation of the intervention.

Figure 1. A Conceptual Model Presenting the Variables of the Study

Figure 1. Schematic Presentation of the Study

Research Objective

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of Team-based Learning Strategy and Video-Based Learning Strategy in the Plate Presentation Skills of the Cookery students of a public school.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a quasi-experimental design with descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, percentage distribution and standard deviation will be employed to describe the plate presentation skills of the participants before and after the conduct of intervention. And also, t-test for paired sample will be used to compare the plate presentation skills of the participants before and after the implementation of the intervention. And ANCOVA will be employed to compare the plate presentation skills of each group after the implementation of the intervention.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

<i>Plate Presentation Skills</i>	TEAM-BASED APPROACH					VIDEO-BASED APPROACH				
	Pre test M	Post test M	t	p	Effect Size	Pre-test M	Post test M	t	p	Effect Size
Proper Balance	2.09	3.76	8.63**	.000	-1.58	2.36	3.28	5.15**	.000	-.940
Use of Color	2.43	3.98	6.73**	.000	-1.23	2.36	4.03	10.58*	.000	-1.93
Shape	1.94	3.96	11.87*	.000	-2.17	2.32	4.26	14.96*	.000	-2.73
Use of Garnish	1.90	3.90	18.06*	.000	-3.30	2.43	4.28	14.81*	.000	-2.70
Overall Product	2.63	4.31	12.42*	.000	-2.27	2.93	3.77	4.96**	.000	-.905

Presentatio
n

*Legend: **significant at 0.01 level*

Table 1 presents the test result of the difference in the participants' plate presentation skills before and after the interventions. The overall posttest result shows a significant difference in the students' overall performance in all sub-skills in plate presentation skills.

The result of the study is supported by Galatsopoulou, et.al. (2022) and Kazi, et.al. (2021) that video-based learning enhances the students understanding about plate presentation techniques and its impact on their skills. The result also supports the study of Surgener, et.al. (2021) that utilizing video-based learning presents a promising avenue in enhancing culinary skills. The increase and improvement on the plate presentation skills of the students before and after the video-based learning strategy is supported by the study of Chen, et.al. (2019) and Smith and Anderson (2018). The same study strongly shows the effectiveness of video-based instructions in enhancing learning outcomes and students' engagement, which is also agreed by Johnson, et.al. (2020) that video-based instruction not only improves comprehension and retention but also increases engagement and participation.

Analysis of Covariance for Plate Presentation Skills by Group

	TEAM-BASED APPROACH GROUP	VIDEO- BASED APPROACH GROUP	F	p	Effect Size
Balance	3.74	3.29	9.66**	.003	.145
Color	3.98	4.03	.123	.727	.002
Shape	3.94	4.27	5.37*	.024	.086
Use of Garnish	3.92	4.26	8.91**	.004	.135
Overall Plate Presentation	4.05	4.07	.130	.719	.002

**significant at 0.01 level

* significant at 0.05 level

The results further revealed significant differences in the means of their skills in balance (F=9.66, p = .003), shape (F=5.37, p = .024), and garnish (F=8.91, p = .004) but not in the use of color. Compared to the other subskills of balance, shape, and garnish,

the use of color did not show statistical significance. This could be due to several reasons unique to the Grade 12 TVL student population. For one, plate presentation color choices are very personal and can be impacted by differences in culture as well as personal preferences. Color combinations frequently depend on individual and cultural tastes, in contrast to balance, shape, and garnish, which have clearer, more teachable rules. Another reason could be that students may already have preconceived ideas about the use of color because of their individual preferences and past experiences. It may be difficult to change these pre-existing preferences for color through instructional interventions. By contrast, when structured learning approaches are used, students may be more familiar with ideas like balance, shape, and finish, which may result in more noticeable improvements in the students' plate presentation skills in these areas.

Moreover, the estimated marginal means showed that the team-based approach group had higher plate presentation skills than the video-based approach group in terms of balance, with a mean score of 3.74 compared to the video-based approach group's mean of 3.29. According to Salas et al. (2017), team-based strategies allow students to collaborate with others helping them develop their specific skills and preparing them for the collaborative nature of the workplace. Hence, participating in team-based activities with Grade 12 TVL students likely allowed them to learn from and collaborate with their peers, which improved their understanding of portion sizes and symmetrical plating.

In a nutshell, students in Grade 12 TVL greatly enhance many sub-skills related to plate presentation using both team-based and video-based approaches. The collaborative aspect of the tasks is perhaps the reason why the team-based approach is so effective in promoting balance. By comparison, because of the benefits of visual and repetitive learning, the video-based approach performs better when it comes to improving abilities linked to shape and design. These results imply that the best strategy for developing thorough plate presentation skills in culinary education may include the effective use of varied learning approaches such as team and video-based approaches.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The implementation of team-based learning and video-based learning strategies is very important in teaching not only the plate presentation skills of the students, but in overall skills of TVL students. Teachers who play a vital role in the learning process of the students must consider of not only using the traditional strategies of teaching such as pure discussion, pen-and-paper test, and oral recitation, but also using collaborative learning and using of media to make the learning process more engaging and interesting for the students.

The constructivist learning theory and multimedia learning theory which are the basis for this study were emphasized and confirmed in this study. The students plate presentation skills significantly improve after the implementation of team-based learning and video-based learning strategies. Moreover, team-based learning is found to have a higher difference on the pre-test and post-test scores compared to the video-based

learning. This result emphasizes that collaborative learning is significant in improving the skills of the students.

Teachers, that they may consider utilizing collaborative activities for students to work and learn from their peers and even share their own. Also, using video discussions so that students can rewatch an instruction they need to master. Educational Institutions to consider activities and training that will be helpful for the development of the TVL students to understand the culinary industry. Future researchers may consider the result of this study and increase the number of participants to have a wider scope and understanding on the implementation of different learning strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As stated in RA 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal data must be collected for valid reasons. Both parties giving and receiving information should be aware of it. Thus, the researcher secured an assent form from the parents of the research participants, and attached therewith was the informed consent from their parents/guardians. The confidentiality of the data gathered the risks, and the benefits of their child's participation in the study were also mentioned and explained. The parents/guardians were also informed that their child's participation in the study was voluntary; hence, withdrawing their child's participation at any time was possible.

With that being stated, all data collection was done with permission to ensure the confidentiality of the information. Thus, all personal information must be relevant and used only for the study's intended purpose. The researcher introduced the research purpose to the participants in the first week before administering the interventions. The participants were involved in the study for 5 weeks only. In the first week, after giving orientation, a pre-test was administered on both interventions in each group of respondents. After that, the groups were exposed to different instructional interventions, and the fifth week was the Post-test of each intervention. The learners in both groups took a posttest after the interventions to determine if there were improvements in their plate presentation skills performance.

The ethical considerations of this study, (adapted from Muhammed Hassan, 2023) included transparency, confidentiality, voluntary participation, risks and benefits of the study, and consent and assent for minors.

Transparency. The researcher observed transparency to the participants and people involved in what is the main purpose, goals, and objective of conducting the research. The researcher will read the research problem, significance, and purpose of the research to the participants. The outcomes or results of the research will also be available and transparent to the participants and people involved.

Confidentiality. In line to protect the rights of the study participants, all the information gathered from this study is kept private and confidential. As stated in RA 10173, or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal data must be collected for valid reasons. Both parties giving and receiving information should be aware of it.

Voluntary Participation. The participation of the respondents was completely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy and information was given whenever the respondents do not understand, before deciding whether to participate or not in the study. Respondents' names did not appear anywhere and no one except the researcher knew about respondents' specific scores.

Consents and Assent for Minor. The researcher made sure that the participants of the study were fully aware of the purpose of the study, and the benefits that they and the school got from the study. The study conducted with the approval of the concerned school authorities, parents, and as well as the permission of the respondents themselves.

Risks of Study. During the entire duration of this study, they may get burns from cooking, and cuts while preparing the ingredients. To avoid these dangers, they were required to wear PPE or Personal Protective Equipment such as gloves, apron, hairnet, face mask, and foot socks all the time during the entire duration of the cooking activities. And if these dangers occur, the HE laboratory has its own safety measures corner and a complete set of Medicine and Health kits.

Benefits of Study. Students were given a grade that is according to their performance as a student. Also, this study provided important information that is very useful to the cookery students, to the teachers, and even public and private administrators. The results, discussions, and findings of this study can help teachers to improve strategies that will help them improve your knowledge and skills in plate presentation.

Vulnerability. As school's policy for the safety of its students, for some unavoidable circumstances, the researcher gave consideration and respect to the parents/guardians and the research participants whenever they could not join or participate in the class conducted four times a week to ensure their rights were also observed. The researcher also allocated a specific budget to be given to those research participants who would not be able to provide ingredients.

Collaborative study terms of reference. The researcher will get the approval of the Guidance Designate of the School where the participants are enrolled. After seeking the approval of the school head, the school guidance designate will also be oriented and informed about the experimental study to secure the rights of the students.

Moreover, a student can withdraw from the study if he/she is not comfortable with the conduct of the study. The participants can leave or opt to not continue his/her participation in the study. With these, the participants can consider the withdrawal criteria in not participating in the study. Lastly, the participant can also inform the researcher, right away, if he/she wishes to withdraw from the study, wherein he/she can provide his/her reason(s) for withdrawing from the study but is not required to provide one.

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